

CULTURAL COMPETENCY AND DIVERSITY IN NURSING PRACTICE: ASSESSING THE INFLUENCE ON TEAMWORK, COMMUNICATION, AND PATIENT OUTCOMES

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18671890>

Key words:

Cultural competence, teamwork, communication, patient's outcome

Abstract: *The increasing cultural diversity in healthcare in European countries, including Austria, has highlighted the need to enhance nurses' cultural competence. Assessing cultural competence and identifying relevant influencing factors can help to improve culturally competent care. The aim of this study was to assess Cultural Competency and Diversity in Nursing Practice: Assessing the Influence on Teamwork, Communication, and Patient Outcomes. A cross-sectional design was used. Data collection was carried out in April 2025 with nurses and nursing students in the last year of their studies who were working in two teaching hospitals in Port Harcourt, Rivers State. Descriptive analysis was applied to display the general characteristics of the study participants and the levels of their overall cultural competence. The study revealed that 51 respondents representing 18.3% were between 20 – 30years, 124 respondents corresponding to 41.3 % were between 31–40 years, 103 respondents representing 34.4% were between 41 – 50 years while 18 (6%) were between 51 years and above. The study further revealed that the nurses' cultural competence level was moderate to high (mean = 3.89; SD = .48). Cultural Competency and Diversity in Nursing Practice influences teamwork, communication and patient's outcome. The study concludes that providing culturally competent healthcare services for culturally diverse patients is essential for all healthcare professionals, and especially for nurses who spend the most time with patients. The study therefore recommends that effective interventions, such as educational training need to be implemented in order to deliver culturally competent care and potentially reduce disparities in healthcare and improve patient outcomes.*

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Advance Journal of Nursing and Clinical Practice

Adv. J. Nur. Pract.

Vol. 9; Issue 01;

January–February, 2026

ISSN: 2573 –1134

Impact Factor: 6.94

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.net/Journals/index.php/ajncp/index>

Introduction

The increasing cultural diversity in healthcare in Africa countries, including Nigeria, has highlighted the need to enhance nurses' cultural competence (Jongen et al., 2018). The dynamic process of developing the capacity to deliver effective, safe, and quality care to the patients via considering their diverse cultural elements" is the definition of cultural competence, according to Sharifi et al. (2018). To exhibit cultural competency, healthcare providers must recognize and respect cultural differences and provide treatment that is sensitive to cultural diversity (Kaihlainen et al., 2019). McFarland and Wehbe-Alamah (2018) have recognized cultural competency as a critical component in mitigating healthcare inequities and enhancing patient outcomes, such as patient satisfaction. Care that is culturally competent is cognizant of the consequences for the patient's culture.

According to Antón-Solanas et al. (2021) it entails the purposeful, culturally sensitive use of health and care knowledge to manage the needs of people or groups and assist them in achieving optimal health and well-being or in coping with diseases, disorders, and death. Research has shown that nurses who provide culturally competent nursing care have the ability to increase patient happiness, fight prejudice in healthcare, and enhance the quality-of-care Ervin et al., (2016). According to Cai et al. (2021), all of these factors improve patient outcomes from a variety of cultural backgrounds (e.g., treatment adherence) (Červený et al., 2019).

High-level culturally competent nurses can communicate with patients more effectively, which may aid in the creation of suitable therapies (Lin et al., 2018).

The majority of nurses in Africa said that caring for patients from diverse cultural backgrounds presented difficulties. The primary obstacles identified were linguistic disparities, religious beliefs, and inadequate cultural awareness (Cervený et al., 2020). These results demonstrate the need for cultural competency tests and enhancements among Nigerian nurses. Additionally, academics and healthcare professionals may create targeted treatments (such cultural diversity training programs) to fulfill the requirements of nurses by evaluating and identifying numerous aspects that impact cultural competency (Osmanovic et al., 2020). However, there is currently a dearth of study on Nigerian nurses' cultural competency. Despite a few international research looking at variables influencing cultural competency, there is insufficient evidence to apply these results to Nigerian nurses (Caricati et al., 2016). According to Lin et al.'s research from 2021, pre-graduate nursing students seem to be more affected by cultural competency education than registered nurses are, however registered nurses' cultural competency is unaffected by it (Lin et al., 2018). According to a different research, nurses with more experience and who have had diversity training have noticeably greater levels of cultural competency (Lin et al., 2018). Based on these results, academics and healthcare professionals

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may better create coherent treatments and provide culturally competent care by evaluating the cultural competence of Nigerian nurses and identifying the elements that impact their competence.

As far as we are aware, no prior research has used a psychometrically validated tool to evaluate the cultural competency of Nigerian nurses. Thus, the purpose of this research was to evaluate the impact of cultural competency and diversity in nursing practice on patient outcomes, teamwork, and communication.

Aims and Objectives of the study

The study is aimed at assessing Cultural Competency and Diversity in Nursing Practice: Assessing the Influence on Teamwork, Communication, and Patient Outcomes. The specific objectives are to;

1. Ascertain the influence of Cultural Competency and Diversity in Nursing Practice on Teamwork among nurses.
2. Examine the influence of Cultural Competency and Diversity in Nursing Practice on Communication among nurses.
3. Assess the influence of Cultural Competency and Diversity in Nursing Practice on Patient Outcomes.

Methodology

This study adopted a descriptive cross-sectional survey design. The population comprised all the nurse-midwives in the 31 departments of UPTH and 10 departments of RSUTH. -By estimate, based on 2020 record, in UPTH, there are 899 nurse-midwives while in RSUTH, there are 438

nurse-midwives. Thus, 1337 nurse-midwives make up this study population. The sample size of 394 was selected from the total population of 1337 representing 29.47%. The study adopted a self-structured validated instrument titled, “Cultural Competency and Diversity in Nursing Practice: Assessing the Influence on Teamwork, Communication, and Patient Outcomes Questionnaire” (CCDNPTCPOQ). The instrument was divided in two (2) sections: A, and B. Section A consisted of demographic information of the respondents, while section B sought information on research variables of this study. The instrument consists of a-25 questionnaire item, which was structured on A four-point Likert scale require the respondents to respond on the options of: Strongly Agree (A), Agree (A) Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD). The Likert scale have ratings of: 4, 3, 2, and 1 respectively. The researcher self-administered the instrument (CCDNPTCPOQ) with the assistance of two trained research assistants. They were pre-informed on the need and modalities for administering the instrument (CCDNPTCPOQ). The administered copies were filled in an average of 6 minutes and were retrieved immediately. Out of the 394 copies of the instrument administered, 360 copies were retrieved and completely filled representing 98.08% return rate. The objectives were addressed using frequency, charts, mean, simple percentage, and standard deviation. The mean of 2.5 was used as criterion mean. Thus, mean of 2.5 and above were remarked as ‘agreed’ for

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response to items measured with agreed and disagreed. Additionally, inferential statistics (z-test analysis) was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Inclusion and exclusion criteria

Nurse who accepted to be part of the study were included while the nurses who declined were excluded.

Results

Fig 1: Age distribution of respondents

In Fig 1, it was shown that 51 respondents representing 18.3% were between 20 – 30years, 124 respondents corresponding to 41.3 % were

between 31 – 40 years, 103 respondents representing 34.4% were between 41 – 50 years while 18 (6%) were between 51 years and above.

Figure 2: Respondents years of experience

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Fig. 2 shows that 15.5% of the respondents had less than 1 year work experience, 37.3% had 1 – 5years working experience, 27.4% had 6 –

10years working experience while 19.8% had more that 11years working experience.

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Table 1 influence of Cultural Competency and Diversity in Nursing Practice on Teamwork among nurses

Cultural Competence items	Mean (SD)
I work with all my colleagues irrespective of their culture or religion	4.23 (.79)
I know about cultures so; I can flow with anyone at work	4.05 (.95)
I believe that everyone, regardless of their cultural heritage, should be treated with respect	4.92 (.38)
I understand that people from different cultures can define the concept of “health care” in different ways so I communicate to know their view.	4.47 (.79)
I think that my knowledge about different cultural groups can help me in my work with individuals, families, and groups.	4.44 (.78)
I seek information about cultural needs when I meet new people at my work or educational institution	3.02 (1.08)
I ask people to tell me about their expectations regarding nursing care services	3.36 (1.16)
I avoid using generalizations to apply stereotypes to groups of people	4.14 (.78)
I recognize potential barriers to healthcare services that different people might encounter	3.64 (.69)
I remove barriers regarding nursing services affecting people from different cultural backgrounds, when I identify them	3.86 (.84)
I remove barriers for people from different cultures, when they tell me about them	3.84 (.84)
I gladly accept feedback from clients on how I relate to people from different cultures	4.33 (.85)
I find possibilities to adapt my nursing services to fit the cultural preferences of individuals and groups	3.60 (.85)

SD Standard deviation

Table 2 influence of Cultural Competency and Diversity in Nursing Practice on Communication among nurses

Cultural Competence items	Mean (SD)
Communication at work place can be very easy if you understand cultural differences	4.03 (.79)
I can very expressive when I meet people from other culture or religion	3.05 (.95)
I do not like to talk to people who are not of the same culture with me.	1.92 (.38)
I am interested in listening well before moving on to the next questions when communicating with people who are different	3.47 (.79)
I make sure I discuss with my people about their views	2.84 (.84)
I gladly accept feedback from clients on how I relate to people from different cultures	3.33 (.85)

SD Standard deviation

Table 3 influence of Cultural Competency and Diversity in Nursing Practice on Patient Outcomes.

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Cultural Competence items	Mean (SD)
When you care about a patient indiscriminately, the patient gets well fast	3.05 (.95)
Cultural competence leads to negative patient outcome.	1.92 (.38)
Patient feel comfortable with nurses who attend to them without discrimination	3.47 (.79)

SD Standard deviation

Discussion

The link between teamwork and cultural competency emphasizes the need of developing culturally competent health systems even more. Developing organizational cultural competency might be a key strategy for promoting high-performing teams. Organizational norms and environment are considered collaboration input elements in both the slightly modified (IMO) and classic (IPO) frameworks of teamwork. Kuntzle (2018) despite the fact that team inputs have not gotten much attention in the literature up to this point, it is known that a team's operational environment plays a vital role in how well the team functions (Mathieu et al., 2018). Our research indicates a relationship between cultural competency and collaboration. The organizational context of team inputs may benefit from investments made in cultural competency at the systems level, according to our results.

Organizational cultural competency may impact the environment of cooperation in a number of ways. Creating a diverse workforce and leadership team may improve communication and approachability at work. Educating people about diversity may raise knowledge of how to collaborate with coworkers and patients from

various backgrounds. Actually, strengthening communication—a crucial component of productive teamwork—and raising self-awareness of attitudes toward members of other racial and ethnic groups are among the main goals of diversity training. (Dreachslin, Sinioris, and Curtis, 2017) By fostering more productive teams, organizational cultural competency may boost employee retention and work satisfaction. For nursing assistants working in long-term care institutions, one of the best indicators of job satisfaction was perceptions of organizational cultural competence. (Davies Allensworth et al., 2017)

In nations like Nigeria, where racial and cultural diversity is expanding quickly and is therefore becoming more prevalent among professionals in the healthcare industry, evaluating nurses' cultural competency is crucial. The cultural competency levels of Nigerian nurses and nursing students working in acute care settings are now being better understood thanks to this research. Participants had high levels of cultural awareness (mean = 4.42; SD = 0.45) and moderate levels of cultural competence behavior (mean = 3.59; SD = 0.59), with an overall level of cultural competence that was moderate to high. According to Truong et al. (2014), the authors of

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two studies conducted in nearby countries, Slovakia and Italy, used the same instrument to evaluate nurses' cultural competency, and the findings are consistent with our own. In addition to being able to identify parallels and variations in cultural expression, nurses with high levels of cultural awareness often show respect and an open mind toward cultural diversity. According to Doorenbos et al. (2016), these skills are necessary for obtaining cultural competency in practice. The characteristics of cultural competency include implementing cultural assessment in the workplace, getting patient feedback on their needs and expectations for treatment, modifying interventions to take into account cultural customs, and requesting more resources and information (Oikarainen et al., 2019). The study's identification of a modest degree of cultural competence behavior among nurses suggests that Nigerian nurses' capacity to identify and attend to cultural demands in their day-to-day work is still limited.

As compared to nurses in Slovakia (Schim et al., 2018) and Italy (Cicolini et al., 2019), the nurses' self-perceived levels of cultural competency were greater in our research. The self-perceived degree of cultural competence in African nations seems to remain low, nevertheless, when contrasted with that of nations such as the United States, where nursing practice has long emphasized and taught cultural competency. It is evident from the research by Doorenbos et al. (2016) that 92.7% of the participants felt extremely competent or moderately competent.

Conclusions

The need to provide culturally competent healthcare in Africa and specifically in Nigeria is changing due to ongoing demographic changes. Results of this study show that the nurses' cultural competence level was moderate to high. In self-assessment of their knowledge of transcultural communication, they rated themselves very high but acknowledged cognitive deficiencies in the history of cultures, individual history, and limited knowledge, mainly in matters of internal diversity.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the study recommends that;

1. Effective interventions, such as educational training events or programs designed to meet nurses' needs, need to be implemented in Nigerian hospitals in order to promote culturally competent nursing care.
2. Further research is deemed necessary to examine how other relevant variables influence cultural competence.
3. Senior leaders of health systems should consider investment in cultural competence as a contributor toward team effectiveness. Specifically, organizations may help support cultural competence by committing resources to the following: developing a comprehensive plan that addresses patients' cultural needs, recruiting and retaining a diverse staff and leadership, collaborating with the community, recognizing and rewarding care that meets

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patients' cultural needs, and providing adequate

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